

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

May 2025

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Purpose

The purpose of the data management plan is to provide guidance on how best to collect, store, secure and share data generated by the 1KSA Project. This plan was created during the pilot phase of 1KSA (September 2023 to March 2024) after addressing challenges around data transfer and storage. Version 2 includes updates made between April 2024 and April 2025. This document will aid in managing the data effectively **across the data lifecycle (Figure 1)**. This data management plan is a **living document** and will be updated as the project develops and as the data management strategy is refined. *Suggested changes to this document can be sent to information@diplomics.org.za.*

Figure 1: The Data Management Cycle

Description of the data

1KSA is a flagship project initiated by DIPLOMICS to sequence the genomes of over 1000 species important to South African biodiversity. DIPLOMICS Training Lab and partner labs (**Figure 2**) will be used to generate whole genome sequencing (WGS) data using Oxford Nanopore Technology, specifically using the PromethION (PromethION 24 and PromethION P2Solo).

Figure 2: 1KSA Partner Labs.

DIPLOMICS Training Lab; University of Pretoria Genomics Lab (UPGL); CenGen; South African Institute for Aquatic Biodiversity (SAIAB) and University of the Western Cape (IMBM), South African Medical Research Council Genomics Lab

Each of these labs have access to a PromethION sequencing device (P24 or P2Solo) which will be used to conducted whole genome sequencing (WGS) of South African species. **Table 1** summarises the different data captured and generated by the 1KSA Project. The formats allow for interoperability of the data. The software used is well established, maintained, and free to use which enables sharing and long-term validity and use of the data.

Table 1: Data Summary

Data	Description	Format
Administrative records	Contributor details (name, affiliation), ethics and permits, 1KSA T&Cs	Captured in REDCap. Exportable as .csv or .pdf report
Species metadata	Species importance, taxonomy, collection information, permit information, location (provincial level)	Captured in REDCap. Exportable as .csv or .pdf report. Copy of permits backed-up on DIPLOMICS Dropbox account
Sample data	DNA sample quality measures and fragmentation analysis.	Captured in REDCap. Exportable as .csv or .pdf report
Raw genome sequencing data (ONT)	Raw genetic sequencing data generated by PromethION sequencing machines (P2Solo or P24).	Pod5 and fastq files. Pod5 files are tar.gz compressed into one object and fastq files are concatenated.
Raw sequencing data information	File size, checksums, storage locations and analysis progress.	Captured in REDCap. Exportable as .csv or .pdf report
Draft genome assembly	Raw data are processed with, KMC, NanoPlot assembled with Flye, and polished with Racon.	.html reports .fasta file

Data	Description	Format
Genome assembly evaluation scores	Assemblies are evaluated with Quast and BUSCO	Html reports Text files Captured in REDCap. Exportable as .csv or .pdf report

Data collection / generation

Methodologies

DNA or tissue samples (method development projects only) will be sent to one of the 1KSA partner labs (UPGL, SAIAB, UWC, DIPLOMICS Training Lab, SAMRC Genomics Platform) for DNA library preparation and whole genome sequencing using PromethION flow cells on P2 or P24 sequencing devices.

The output from a genome sequencing run includes, fastq and pod5 files. The fastq files can immediately be used in the **genome assembly workflow (<https://github.com/DIPLOMICS-SA>)**. Pod5 files may be used to re-do basecalling when an improved version of the basecalling algorithm is released. Therefore, it is important that the pod5 files are securely stored long term and well curated. These data are intended to become a national resource for South African researchers, for South African Biodiversity.

Data quality and standards

Data such as species information, DNA and library preparation quality metrics will be captured in REDCap. DNA or libraries that do not meet the minimum quality measures will not be sequenced. In some cases DNA will first be run on the MinION to ensure that the DNA is of sufficient purity to not block the pores. REDCap will be used to create checklists and reports to document data generation and track progress per species sequencing project. Upon completion of a species sequencing project there will be a 2 person sign off process to ensure all the data are captured and stored correctly.

Data management, documentation, and curation

Figure 2: Key resources in the data management of 1KSA

Managing, storing and curating data.

- Sample contributor details and species information are captured via a REDCap “sample submission” survey link sent to the contributor upon successful application to participate in 1KSA. Data entered by the contributor are checked for completion and accuracy by a member of the 1KSA team.
- Lab data (DNA quality control, library preparation and sequencing run parameters) are entered into REDCap by a laboratory technician.
- Raw sequencing data are generated on PromethION P2/P24 sequencing devices. Data are then stored in-house at networked attached storage (NAS) locations or suitable large external hard drives.
- Fastq and pod5 (pass) files are transferred, via Globus Connect, to CHPC for genome assembly.
- Fastq files are concatenated into one file which is then used as the input file for the draft genome assembly pipeline, which generates one fasta file.
- Pod5 files are tar.gz compressed, transferred via Globus Connect along with the fastq and fasta files, and are stored at DIRISA for long term storage. Pod5 files can be used at a later stage to redo basecalling when a new basecalling algorithm is released or if the fastq files get deleted. **Table 2** summarises the storage locations.
- REDCap is used to curate and track project progress and the data (**Figure 3**).
 - There are 10 data collection instruments used to capture and track data at every stage of the project.
 - Reports are then exported and shared with the Sample Contributor / student.

Data Collection Instrument
1KSA Sample Submission (survey)
Ethics and Permits
Sample Delivery
Library Prep and Sequencing
Data Analysis
Data Storage
Data Shared with Contributor
Species Genome Card
Project Report
Species Complete

Figure 3: REDCap Data Collection Instruments

Table 2: Storage Locations

1. Sequencer	2. NAS	3. CHPC	4. DIRISA
Data are generated by the PromethION and stored in /Data/Experiment_Name	The whole experiment directory is copied from the sequencer to the NAS. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Run reports Other reports Fastq_pass Fastq_fail Pod5_pass Pod5_fail REDCap Project back ups 	A subset of files of copied to the CHPC for analysis and file compression <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fastq_pass Pod5_pass 	For long term storage: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fastq_pass.tar.gz Pod5_pass..tar.gz Run report Nanoplot reports BUSCO output Quast output Polished.fasta REDCap Project back ups

The whole experiment directory is deleted when data are securely stored on both the NAS AND DIRISA

Fastq_fail and pod5 files can be deleted.

Uncompressed and compressed files must be deleted from the CHPC when data are securely stored on the NAS AND DIRISA

The DIRISA collection must be shared with the contributor.

NAS: Network attached storage; CHPC: Centre For High Performance Computing; DIRISA; Data Intensive Research Initiative of South Africa.

Figure 1: Data movement and storage locations

Metadata standards and data documentation

1KSA data are intended to create a digital research infrastructure and therefore will be shared and used by others outside the 1KSA team. All data are eventually captured in REDCap. For example, information from lab books during DNA quality control, library prep and sequencing are entered into REDCap on a weekly basis. REDCap has a data dictionary function to explain the different variables (field names) used in the project for ease of use.

A well-documented draft genome assembly is available on GitHub to enable others to understand the analysis and to re-generate the outputs from this project. All 1KSA documentation is version controlled and are shared on [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org).

Data preservation strategy and standards

The most important files are the Pod5 files because they can be used to regenerate the fastq and bam files if needed. Therefore, Pod5 files will be stored at DIRISA for > 10 years. As an additional back up, Pod5 files will also be stored on a NAS at the Centre for Genomic and Proteomic Research (CPGR, host of DIPLOMICS). REDCap will be used to document data storage locations and will be able to link files with their corresponding metadata. Regular backup of the REDCap database will also be stored on both DIRISA and the NAS.

At present the DIPLOMICS Bioinformatics coordinator is designated data manager of 1KSA. However, the accounts set up are not linked to the persons personal/employee email in order to ease hand-over of responsibilities when necessary.

Data security

Data will be securely stored at DIRISA with password protected, limited access. Likewise, data stored on NAS locations will have be password protected with limited access. Data will not freely accessible /downloadable. Data will be known – i.e. the existence of the data will be documented on the 1KSA website and access to the data will be determined by a Data Access Committee.

The 1KSA project is not sequencing human DNA.

Table 3: Risks to Data and Mitigation Strategies

#	Risk	Mitigation
1	Data loss	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A minimum of 2 copies of the data exist at all times. - Pod5 files are securely stored to be used to re-generate data if needed.
2	Data corruption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Globus Connect is used transfer large data files. - Md5sum checks are performed captured on REDCap.
3	Loss of access to data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure up to date, thorough documentation and make sure any hand-over is conducted properly

Data sharing and access

Data will be stored at DIRISA. DIPLOMICS will make all the sequencing data and genome assembly outputs available to the Sample Contributor and for a three period, the Sample Contributor is free to use and re-analyse this data. However, permission must be sought from the 1KSA Data Access Committee (DAC) prior to publications involving the raw data. Please refer to the Terms of use on the website. The DAC will also evaluate other applications for access to the data. Within three years of sequencing, the sample Contributor will be consulted. If the request is approved, it will be under the conditions of a Data Transfer Agreement.

Suitability for sharing

1KSA will not share any GPS coordinates of species sampling location

Discovery by potential users of the research data

1KSA will publicize the generation of sequencing data for each species. This will be done, for example by means of a species report card published on the 1KSA website or other media channels. This will allow these data to be *known*. However, and very importantly, not freely downloadable, or available. In addition, DIPLOMICS and 1KSA will share method development protocols and project documentation on [Zenodo](#) in the spirit of **Open Science**.

Governance of access

The 1KSA Data Access Committee will meet on a monthly basis and review any applications for data access. Data access will be accompanied by a **Data Transfer Agreement**.

Definitions

Term	Definition
CHPC	Centre for High Performance Computing

CPGR	Centre for Proteomic and Genomic Research
DIRISA	Data Intensive Research Infrastructure of South Africa
NAS	Network attached storage
SAIAB	South African Institute for Aquatic Biodiversity
SAMPLE CONTRIBUTOR	Often PI on project. Has the authority and necessary ethics and permits to contribute the sample and data to 1KSA.
SGL	SAMRC Genomics Laboratory
UPGL	University of Pretoria Genomics Laboratory
WGS	Whole genome sequencing

Version history

Version	Date Modified	Significant changes	Author	Next review date*
0.1	08-08-2023	Document created	P Swart	-
1.0	19-03-2024	Document finalised for Zenodo	P Swart	19-07-2024
1.1	26-02-2025	Minor corrections, DAC information, added SAMRC GL	P Swart, S Murray	
2.0	12-05-2025	Changes implemented	S. Murray	30 April 2026

**This document will be reviewed and revised every 12 months*